

NEMYSHLIA/CSM

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Conceptual Site Model (CSM) of Petroleum Hydrocarbon Contamination in the Nemyshlianskyi District and the Nemyshlia River Floodplain-Pond System

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1. Introduction

The Preliminary Investigation Report on petroleum hydrocarbon contamination (hereinafter referred to as "the contamination") of the Nemyshlianskyi District territory and the Nemyshlia River floodplain-pond system has been prepared in accordance with the objectives of the Memorandum of Cooperation and Understanding concluded between the Department of Construction and Road Management of the Kharkiv City Council, the Research Institution "Ukrainian Scientific Research Institute of Ecological Problems," and SafeLine LLC, dated February 16, 2026.

The objective of the preliminary investigation is to develop an initial Conceptual Site Model (CSM) of the contamination resulting from a spill of petroleum products during the attack on the KhBN-Rezerv LLC oil depot in February 2024 (hereinafter referred to as the "CSM of the contamination") to identify and verify threats using threshold regulatory indicators and to define remediation goals.

The CSM of the contamination was developed

In accordance with the standard:

DSTU ISO 10381-5:2009 "Soil quality — Sampling — Part 5: Guidance on the procedure for the investigation of urban and industrial sites with regard to soil contamination"

In accordance with the methodology:

LNAPL-3: LNAPL Site Management: LCSM Evolution, Decision Process, and Remedial Technologies», Interstate Technology and Regulatory Council, USA

Based on the input data:

Annotated Scientific and Technical Report "Investigation and Assessment of the Environmental Status for the periods: July–September 2024, October–December 2024, and January–April 2025," Research Institution "Ukrainian Scientific Research Institute of Ecological Problems," in 8 volumes;

Scientific and Technical Research Report "Socio-economic Assessment of the Population of the Nemyshlianskyi District of Kharkiv Affected by the Explosion and Fire at the Oil Depot Resulting from Shelling by the Russian Federation, Based on Field Research (Surveys)," LLC NTVK "Ukraine," Kharkiv, 2024

Geotechnical Investigation Report for the project "Reconstruction of the Open Drainage System along Yaseneva St., on the section from Vysokohirna St. to Traktorobudivnykiv Ave. in Kharkiv," Khorda-UA LLC, 2024

Field Observation Results from the Contamination Site Inspection, SafeLine LLC, December 2025

The CSM of the contamination was developed based on the analysis of relevant lines of evidence (LoE) encompassing microbiology, hydrogeology, petrochemistry, and geochemistry; it will require hypothesis verification and refinement of contamination boundaries during further field investigations involving sampling and analysis.

The developed CSM of the contamination integrates information regarding concerns, exposure pathways, and receptors to support cost-effective management decisions regarding the remediation strategy for the contaminated ecosystem of the Nemyshlianskyi District.

2. Characteristics of the Nemyshlianskyi District

The topography of the Nemyshlianskyi District area in Kharkiv, which was affected by the contamination, is formed by the Nemyshlia River valley slope and exhibits a distinct terraced structure.

The upper part of the slope is dominated by loess terraces composed of silty-loam parent deposits overlain by a layer of chernozems with varying degrees of transformation, characterized by medium density and relatively good water permeability. The soil cover thickness typically ranges from 110 to 120 cm, while the humus horizon extends to a depth of 40–50 cm with a humus content of up to 8%.

The middle part of the slope corresponds to the level of the lower loess terraces, composed of loams and loess-like loams with inclusions of deluvial deposits, while the soil cover is represented by solonetzic chernozems and, in places, solonetz soils, characterized by increased density, reduced hydraulic conductivity, and a tendency for salt accumulation.

Within the valley, the parent materials are represented by alluvial and alluvial-deluvial deposits composed of loams, sandy loams, and sands, upon which the soil cover, represented by podzolic soils, has formed, characterized by increased water permeability, a leaching water regime, and a relatively low humus content.

The district's climate is classified as temperate continental, belonging to the southern forest-steppe zone. Average monthly air temperatures exceeding 0°C occur from April to November, while temperatures above 15°C are observed from May to September.

Figure 1. Site Location Map, Nemyshlianskyi District, Kharkiv

During the winter months, the average soil surface temperature differs slightly from the average air temperature, and the lowest average monthly soil temperature of -7°C is observed in January. In March, the soil temperature remains negative at approximately -1°C , after which it increases to about $+18^{\circ}\text{C}$ in May. In summer, the soil temperature gradually rises to $+26^{\circ}\text{C}$ in July; during the summer months, it is typically $3\text{--}5^{\circ}\text{C}$ higher than the air temperature. The decline in soil temperature begins in August; however, in November, the average soil surface temperature remains positive at $+1^{\circ}\text{C}$.

The soil temperature within the humus layer at various depths changes significantly slower and undergoes substantially smaller fluctuations; however, throughout the year, the soil temperature follows the trend of its surface temperature. On average, the annual number of days with a soil temperature of 0°C or below is approximately 87 days at a depth of 0.25 m and about 36 days at a depth of 0.5 m; only the upper soil layer, reaching a depth of approximately 50–60 cm, freezes to sub-zero temperatures annually.

In terms of atmospheric precipitation, the district belongs to a zone of insufficient moisture: the average annual precipitation is approximately 528 mm, featuring a characteristic continental annual cycle with a maximum in summer months and a minimum in winter. Precipitation exceeding 8 mm within 12 hours is considered significant; on average, approximately 13 such 12-hour intervals occur per year, predominantly during the warm season.

3. Characteristics of the Contamination Site

The site affected by the contamination is characterized as a complex urban-natural ecosystem that combines industrial and residential zones with the Nemyshlia River floodplain-pond system.

Figure 2. Contamination Site Map

The industrial zone is located on the upper part of the hill and includes privately owned enterprises involved in cable manufacturing, industrial powder coating, the production of oilfield and power equipment, petroleum product and rolled metal storage facilities, and wholesale chemical trade, indicating long-term anthropogenic pressure on the environment. The site infrastructure in the industrial zone is characterized by a predominance of impermeable surfaces: production and storage areas are constructed of concrete or consist of graded compacted soil; access roads are primarily made of reinforced concrete slabs, and the site perimeter is defined by concrete fencing.

The residential zone is situated on the hillside and is characterized by dense low-rise housing, comprising more than 332 private households with garden plots. A significant number of these properties are currently unoccupied due to soil contamination with petroleum products. Among the remaining residents, elderly individuals predominate, for whom growing produce on their garden plots is a vital source of food. While the households are connected to centralized water supply and sanitation systems, a significant portion of the residents historically utilizes groundwater from boreholes and wells, particularly for irrigation.

In the past, land grading was widely practiced by backfilling with construction and industrial waste, which facilitated the leaching of pollutants and groundwater contamination [1]. The street network is formed of fill material that has undergone natural compaction due to long-term vehicle and pedestrian traffic. Similar to the industrial zone, the residential area is equipped with a storm drainage system.

The floodplain-pond system is located in the valley and includes the Nemyshlia River channel, the floodplain, and artificial water bodies, specifically Petrynkivskyi Pond and a smaller, unnamed pond (hereinafter referred to as the "Small Pond"). The Small Pond was likely formed by constructing a dam in a depression of the river channel to support the operations of the Nemyshlia sand quarry, while Petrynkivskyi Pond was formed later as a result of flooding the exhausted quarry. Currently, these water bodies are used as urban recreational sites for swimming, fishing, and leisure activities.

The Nemyshlia River floodplain is characterized by the presence of standing water, thick silt deposits, and dense reed beds. The floodplain is recharged by river water, snowmelt, and rainfall, as well as groundwater discharge. The water level in the river and the floodplain is determined by the spring flood (late February – early March) and the prolonged summer-autumn (starting late April – early May) and winter low-flow periods. During the spring flood, the floodplain is inundated to a depth of 1.0 to 3.0 m for a period of 10–15 days. In certain years, rain-induced floods during the low-flow period cause short-term level rises reaching 0.5–1.0 m, and occasionally 1.6–2.0 m. Ice cover is established in the second half of November to the first half of December, with an average duration of 2.5–3.0 months.

A green buffer zone covered with natural herbaceous, shrub, and woody vegetation is situated between the floodplain-pond system and the residential area.

The Nemyshlia River belongs to the Siverskyi Donets River basin; within the potential extent of the contamination plume are riparian neighborhoods of Kharkiv and 17 villages in the Kharkiv region, with a total population of approximately 43,900 people.

4. History of the Petroleum Product Spill

At 22:46 on February 9, 2024, the KhBN-Rezerv LLC oil depot, with a design storage capacity of 6,100 tons in nine above-ground storage tanks (ASTs), was struck by unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs).

As a result of the explosion and damage to part of the above-ground storage tanks, an estimated 3,000–4,000 tons [5] of diesel fuel and gasoline [6] were released, accompanied by a large-scale fire. According to eyewitnesses, "the explosion literally sprayed the fuel around; fuel and lubricants landed on building roofs, trees, and into yards" [3].

Figure 3. Fire resulting from the attack on the KhBN-Rezerv LLC oil depot

The absence or failure of secondary containment structures at the oil depot during the attack led to a "fuel leak onto the street (Yaseneva) and subsequent flow down toward residential buildings" [5], [6]; petroleum products, "mixed with snow, flowed down the street (Yaseneva)" [2]. Given the street's gradient of approximately 5%, the presence of reinforced concrete slab paving, and concrete fencing of industrial enterprises on both sides, the spilled petroleum products spread along the street primarily through surface runoff toward the topographic depression and via soil infiltration in road sections not equipped with slabs.

At the intersection of Yaseneva Street and Vysokohirna Street, a portion of the petroleum product flow entered an earthen drainage ditch with a rectangular profile. This ditch is a component of the municipal storm drainage system that discharges into the Nemyshlia River, downstream of the Traktorobudivnykiv Avenue bridge.

Another portion of the flow continued along Yaseneva Street and subsequently onto Kotelna Street, which has a gradient exceeding 7%. According to the head of the regional police investigation department, "the scene is not (just) this street (Kotelna); it is effectively a small neighborhood. It is

not one street, Kotelna, but the streets along which the burning fuel flowed" [6]. The fire spread to the adjacent residential areas of Yaseneva and Kotelna Streets, resulting in the destruction and damage of 15 residential houses and 7 fatalities [7].

Figure 4. Kotelna Street after the petroleum product spill

Other streets in the area show no signs of fire, such as charred trees, fences, or buildings, and have higher elevations compared to Yaseneva Street at intersections. This indicates an absence of petroleum product migration via surface runoff along these streets; however, their contamination could have occurred as a result of fuel scattering during the explosion.

Spreading down the road paved with compacted fill material on Kotelna Street, a portion of the petroleum products infiltrated the soil and entered sewer manholes located along the road near the households. In the valley, at the intersection with Nemyshlianska Street, the flow of petroleum products, along with meltwater, entered the municipal storm drainage system, through which it subsequently reached the floodplains of Petrynkivskyi and Small Ponds [3].

The floodplain, characterized by a lack of stable water exchange and dense reed beds, acted as a natural filter along the pollution migration path, retaining the bulk of heavy petroleum fractions. However, it contains a section not separated from Petrynkivskyi Pond by an earthen berm, through which light petroleum fractions entered the Nemyshlia River.

Through the Nemyshlia River, the contamination plume spread to the Kharkiv, Lopan, Udy, and Siverskyi Donets rivers [12]. According to the State Environmental Inspection [2], the concentration of petroleum products in the river water at a distance of up to 27 km from the incident site exceeded the maximum allowable concentration (MAC) by 7–8 times, while in the Nemyshlia River, it reached 95 times the limit.

According to environmental activists [4], on the fifth day following the spill, containment booms were installed on the rivers and sorbents were applied. In the areas most heavily impacted by the surface spill, the upper soil layer was replaced.

Figure 5. Petroleum products in the soil of the berm between the floodplain and Petrynkivskyi Pond at a distance of more than 1 km from the contamination source, December 2025.

In the summer of 2024, the territory was struck by missiles for a second time, resulting in a fire in the floodplain, during which reed beds and light petroleum fractions accumulated on the water surface were burned [8].

According to official information, the area of contaminated soil is 10,000 m² [2], and the surface area of affected river waters is 780,000 m² [5].

5. Priority Contamination Migration Pathways

Priority migration pathways are defined as contaminant distribution channels through which pollution moves at velocities significantly exceeding the migration rate within the surrounding environmental matrix, over greater distances, and in directions that are often unexpected under normal conditions.

The contaminated site is characterized by the following priority migration pathways:

- Scattering of petroleum products during the explosion
- Surface topography (terrain relief)
- Underground utilities
- Municipal storm drainage system
- Upper fill soil layer

5.1 Scattering of petroleum products during the explosion

The scattering of petroleum products resulting from an above-ground storage tank strike by an unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) occurs via the mechanism of hydrodynamic shock [9]. The detonation energy of the warhead is instantaneously transferred to the liquid petroleum products, generating a shock wave that causes the tank walls to rupture. A cavity of gaseous detonation products forms within the liquid mass; its rapid expansion displaces the petroleum products toward the periphery, creating a hydraulic piston effect inside the tank. The expansion of the gas cavity within the limited volume of the tank generates an internal pressure impulse that ejects the petroleum products through the breach and wall ruptures. At high ejection velocities, the jets rapidly disintegrate into droplets. The ejection process occurs prior to ignition; therefore, the petroleum products are dispersed over a significant distance without burning.

Given the nonlinearity of the process, an exact determination of the dispersal distance of petroleum products is impossible, as it is simultaneously influenced by explosion pressure, damage geometry, liquid volume, and the subsequent fragmentation of jets into droplets. Therefore, for a first-approximation engineering assessment, it is advisable to apply a simplified ballistic model of droplet flight as objects at an angle to the horizon, accounting for the initial height. Assuming an initial liquid jet velocity of 111 m/s, recorded in ballistic experiments on hydrodynamic shock [10], a tank height of 12 m, a dispersal angle of approximately 45°, and an aerodynamic drag coefficient for droplets of 0.5, the calculated dispersal zone can be described as a circular area with a radius of approximately 635 m centered at the point of explosion.

According to the simplified model, the dispersal of petroleum products was non-uniform and likely occurred within local areas of the industrial site and across two residential blocks. The residential development is located on the periphery of the calculated dispersal range; therefore, the deposition intensity in this zone was significantly lower compared to the industrial zone. Under conditions of dense development, an additional shielding effect was observed: droplets deposited primarily on roofs, facades, and fences, after which they dripped locally along building perimeters onto the soil as narrow strips. This resulted in discrete surface contamination of the upper soil layer.

The discrete nature of contamination within the petroleum product dispersal zone is confirmed by resident survey results: inhabitants of 1-st Plidnyi Lane estimated the contaminated area at

approximately 15%, whereas residents of Tankova Street, located on the main surface migration path, estimated it at 100% [8].

Following the spreading of petroleum products over the area, the exposed surface area increases sharply, leading to the rapid evaporation of light fractions and the formation of a vapor-air mixture above the spill. Simultaneously, under the influence of turbulent flows and thermal convection, a portion of the liquid is further fragmented into fine droplets, forming a fine-dispersed fuel aerosol. The dispersion of the aerosol cloud can occur over distances of up to several kilometers and is determined by wind direction and convective air currents.

Figure 6. Spatial distribution of surface contamination

Throughout February 9, 2024, under conditions of a light north-easterly wind of 1–3 m/s and sub-zero air temperatures of -2...-4 °C, the aerosol cloud drifted slowly in a south-westerly direction toward Heroiv Kharkova Avenue. Under such meteorological conditions, minor volumes of petroleum products were deposited over a large area, leading to the formation of primarily thin, uniform, and continuous surface contamination across the industrial zone, without the formation of significant local accumulations

5.2 Surface topography

As a result of tank damage, a release of petroleum products occurred within the oil depot's process area. The flow escaped the secondary containment and spill localization zone, spreading across the railway tank car loading rack toward Yaseneva Street through damaged sections of the perimeter fencing.

Subsequent surface migration of the contamination was determined by a combination of topography and engineered site features. The existing surface gradient facilitated the gravity-driven flow of petroleum products, while linear engineered features (fencing, curb beams, reinforced concrete slab paving, and the compacted upper soil layer of the roadway) transformed the streets into directional surface runoff channels.

Figure 7. Primary and secondary surface migration pathways of contamination

The primary surface contamination migration pathway extended along Yaseneva Street to the intersection with Kotelna Street and further along Kotelna Street. Adjacent streets, Vysokohirna and Rodiucha, have higher ground elevations, which restricted the spreading of petroleum products outside the main direction of propagation.

Figure 8. Ground elevations at the intersection of Yaseneva and Kotelna Streets

In a localized section near the intersection with Kotelna Street, Yaseneva Street loses its pronounced gradient, facilitating the redistribution of the petroleum product flow toward Kotelna Street as a lower-lying topographic area.

At the same time, it cannot be ruled out that a certain portion of petroleum products continued to move along Yaseneva Street. This is indirectly suggested by recorded evidence of thermal effects on the first few houses located on Yaseneva Street below the intersection with Kotelna Street. However, the mentioned damage may also have resulted from fire spreading between adjacent buildings, independent of the direct movement of the petroleum product flow.

The migration of petroleum products is corroborated by eyewitness accounts from residents of Kotelna, Tankova, and Mohylevska Streets. Homeowners at 43/1 Mohylevska Street reported that petroleum products flowed across their property, with approximately 200 liters of an oil-water mixture infiltrating the cellar over the course of several months [12]. At 129 Tankova Street, petroleum contamination was detected at a depth exceeding 1 meter during the excavation of the upper soil layer [12].

The results of the chemical analysis of soil water extracts were conducted only for the upper fill layer to a depth of 1 m and do not characterize the extent of the contaminant body in deeper horizons. At the same time, they reflect the boundaries of surface spreading and atmospheric dispersal of petroleum products resulting from the primary spill.

The results obtained confirm the hypothesis regarding the direction of surface spreading. Specifically, elevated soil concentrations of petroleum products were recorded at 41/1 Yaseneva St. (point 5) — up to 40.2 MAC, 30 Kotelna St. (point 9) — up to 13.0 MAC, and 129 Tankova St. (point 26) — up to 9.3 MAC. Conversely, no exceedances of allowable concentrations were detected at 28 Plidna St. (point 15), 22/9 1-st Plidnyi Lane (point 19), 256A Nemyshlianska St. (point 38), 54 Zapovidna St. (point 35), 40 Zapovidna St. (point 34), 22 Zapovidna St. (point 32), and 4 Zapovidna St. (point 31), indicating the limited nature of lateral surface migration of the contamination. The absence of petroleum products in the soil at 64 Mohylevska St. (point 11) is attributed to the fact that the primary flow occurred along the opposite side of the street, which features lower elevations.

Figure 9. Concentrations of petroleum products in the near-surface soil layer and bottom sediments (limit – 500 mg/kg)

5.3 Underground utilities

The streets in the residential zone are equipped with underground gas supply, central water supply, and sewerage networks. During the surface spreading along Kotelna Street, petroleum products entered 12 underground shafts through unsealed reinforced concrete covers located at ground level. Subsequently, the contamination migrated along the linear underground utility. Additional indirect confirmation of this utility's presence is provided by preserved warning markings labeled "GNT-7.5" on two buildings.

Figure 10. Layout of underground utility manhole covers along Kotelna Street

5.4 Municipal storm drainage system

In the process of spreading along the primary surface migration pathway, the contamination was intercepted by elements of the municipal storm drainage system on Yaseneva and Nemyshlianska Streets. Open sections of this system consist of unreinforced rectangular ditches, which transition into closed underground sections made of metal pipes at road crossings. A collector chamber provides the connection between the system's open segments and the underground pipeline section.

As a result of entering the municipal storm drainage system, the contamination migrated into the floodplains of the Petrenkivskyi and Small Pond, as well as directly into the Nemyshlia River. During the inspection of the floodplain during the 2024 summer-autumn low-water period, residues of heavy petroleum fractions were recorded on the surface of the bottom sediments [12].

The outfall into the Small Pond floodplain is partially obstructed by bottom sediments and reeds, which reduces the system's hydraulic capacity. This has led to local flooding of the adjacent area of an abandoned private property on Zapovidna Street.

Figure 11. Layout of the municipal storm drainage system segment involved in the contamination migration process.

5.5 Upper fill soil layer

The upper layer within the primary surface contamination migration pathway is composed of heterogeneous fill soil (loam, chernozem, sand) with construction debris inclusions [11]. The heterogeneous structure of this layer, the lack of natural stratification, and the presence of anthropogenic inclusions cause the formation of local zones of increased permeability and macroporosity. The relatively low bulk density of the soil (15.80 kN/m^3) indirectly indicates increased porosity and a loose fill structure beneath a relatively compacted thin near-surface layer.

These features can form local anthropogenic filtration channels characterized by highly variable flow directions and velocities, which may be several orders of magnitude higher than in a conventionally uniform soil matrix. This environmental structure results in a random and poorly predictable nature of lateral contaminant migration, its high spatial variability, and the complexity of tracking dispersal boundaries. Under these conditions, contamination spreads not as a continuous front but as individual flows along local channels associated with fill soil heterogeneity, compacted surfaces, and zones of anthropogenic disturbance.

Based on the above, it is advisable to identify the potentially contaminated area as a strip of territory within the width of the primary surface migration pathway, bounded in the direction of descending ground elevations by building foundations, which serve as conventional lateral barriers to further lateral spreading of the contaminant flow.

6. Spatial Distribution of the Contaminant Body

The contaminant body refers to a three-dimensional volume within the subsurface matrix of the natural environment, within which the petroleum product is present as a non-aqueous phase in the soil pores. The contaminant body represents a multiphase system where soil pores are simultaneously occupied by water, air, and petroleum products in varying proportions.

In contrast, surface contamination is characterized by the presence of petroleum products as a thin film or coating on the surfaces of vegetation, building structures, or the topsoil layer, without significant penetration into the soil matrix.

Taking into account the priority surface migration pathways and excluding the segments of the municipal storm drainage system, the subsequent analysis of the spatial distribution of the contaminant body within the soil matrix is conducted based on the engineering-geological, geomorphological, and hydrogeological conditions of the site within the following delineated zones:

- The oil depot site
- Urban Streets
- The Nemyshlia River floodplain

6.1 The oil depot site

The oil spill area at the oil depot is confined to the process zone and the railway tank car loading rack, while other parts of the facility experienced significant dispersal of petroleum products resulting from explosions. Satellite imagery analysis indicates that the site, which has been in operation for over 30 years, was in a state of chronic contamination prior to the accident. Evidence includes localized brown stains within the railway loading rack area and a zone of distressed vegetation further downslope.

Figure 12. Evidence of chronic contamination at the oil depot site

Data on the geological structure and groundwater table depth are unavailable. However, given the chronic nature and scale of the accidental spill, it can be assumed that the soils in the vicinity of the oil depot are in a state of mobile oil saturation. In other words, petroleum products occupy a significant portion of the total soil porosity, form an interconnected network, and can move vertically and laterally under pressure gradients, particularly during pumping operations.

6.2 Urban Streets

The spatial distribution of the contaminant body within the soil matrix varies along the primary surface migration pathway of petroleum products due to changes in geological and hydrogeological conditions along the slope. The formation and configuration of the contaminant body are governed by the petroleum flow pressure gradient, soil filtration properties, and the capillary resistance of the pore space.

Given the positive temperatures and periodic light precipitation in the days leading up to the accident, the soils were in a moist state with partial pore saturation, particularly in loams and sandy loams. On the day of the accident, characterized by light precipitation (rain and snow) and sub-zero air temperatures, the upper fill soil layer may have been in a state of localized freezing, leading to a reduction in its hydraulic conductivity and infiltration capacity. The filling of pores with moisture and their localized blocking by ice hindered the rapid vertical penetration of petroleum products into deeper layers.

Under these hydrometeorological and soil conditions, surface and lateral migration of petroleum products predominated, occurring primarily downslope along the interfaces of layers with varying permeability, while vertical infiltration into the soil profile was limited and non-uniform.

Maximum soil pore saturation with petroleum products occurred on slope sections with the highest hydrodynamic pressure—specifically in zones with reduced gradients where the flow velocity decreased, increasing the contact time between the petroleum and the soil, and leading to the formation of local liquid accumulation zones. These include the intersections of Yaseneva–Vysokohirna (2) and Yaseneva–Kotelna (4) Streets, and the section of Kotelna Street from Mohylyvska to Nemyshlianska (7).

Figure 13. Longitudinal topographic profile along the primary surface migration pathway of petroleum products

The baseline data regarding the slope's geological structure are provided based on the results of engineering-geological surveys conducted along Yaseneva Street, from Vysokohirna Street to Traktorobudivnykiv Avenue [11] in September 2024. Geomorphologically, the site is located within the alluvial terraces of the Nemyshlia River, composed of Quaternary alluvial sandy-clay deposits overlain by surface fill soils. Soils down to a depth of 4.0 m consist of six engineering-geological elements (EGE), the presence and thickness of which vary along the slope (see Figure 14).

EGE-1. Fill layer: loam, chernozem, sand with construction debris inclusions; settled, slightly moist, and heterogeneous, with thickness ranging from 0.5 m at the bottom to 1.3 m at the top of the slope. It is characterized by increased filtration capacity and non-uniform permeability.

EGE-2. Topsoil and vegetation layer: black, loamy, humified, with organic matter inclusions and plant roots; loose, with thickness ranging from 0.3 m to 0.5 m. It is characterized by high porosity and permeability, coupled with the high sorption capacity of the organic matter.

EGE-3. Loess-like loam, yellow-brown, hard consistency, collapsible (subsident), with a thickness of 0.7–1.7 m and the following physical and mechanical properties: natural moisture content — 0.16 (as of September), soil density — 1.86 g/cm³, void ratio — 0.79, degree of saturation — 0.6. It is characterized by low filtration capacity and high retention capacity for petroleum products within the pore space. Since a portion of the pores remains air-filled, the penetration of petroleum products into the upper part of the layer is possible; however, the fine-pored structure and capillary forces limit further downward infiltration.

EGE-4. Light brown loam, hard consistency, approximately 0.9 m thick, with the following physical and mechanical properties: natural moisture content — 0.18 (as of September), soil density — 1.93 g/cm³, void ratio — 0.86, degree of saturation — 0.68. It is characterized by slightly higher moisture content and porosity, as well as even lower filtration capacity.

EGE-5. Yellow-grey sandy loam, hard consistency, with a thickness ranging from 1.1 m to 1.6 m and the following physical and mechanical properties: natural moisture content — 0.16 (as of September), soil density — 1.98 g/cm³, void ratio — 0.7, degree of saturation — 0.69. It is characterized by moderate water permeability and a developed macroporous structure.

EGE-6. Grey and greenish-grey sands, fine-grained, medium water saturation, medium density, with the following physical and mechanical properties: natural moisture content — 0.2 (as of September), soil density — 2.1 g/cm³, void ratio — 0.48, degree of saturation — 0.95. The fine-grained structure determines its high filtration capacity.

Figure 14. Engineering-geological cross-section along Yaseneva Street, from Vysokohirna Street to Traktorobudivnykiv Avenue

Table 1

Sect.	Slope	Geo Log	GW	Contaminant body
1	4,0°	EGE-1, EGE-2, EGE-3, EGE-4	> 8 m	The predominant volume of petroleum products migrated via surface runoff. Even the portion of the contamination that infiltrated the soil filled the pore space laterally in the direction of the slope, a process that dominated over vertical infiltration. The main contaminant body is localized within the vadose zone along the fence line and is vertically bounded by the top of the EGE-4 layer at a depth of approximately 3 m. A zone of residual phase saturation has formed within the EGE-1 layer, while the primary mobile phase body is concentrated within the EGE-2 and EGE-3 layers, reaching its maximum thickness at the contact with the EGE-4 aquiclude.
2	0°	EGE-1, EGE-2, EGE-3, EGE-4	> 8 m	Due to the stagnant nature of the spill, the soil matrix from the surface to a depth exceeding 4 m is in a state near full petroleum saturation, localized within the area of lower topographic elevations. The vertical distribution of the contamination follows a "shark fin" model: the bulk of the mobile phase spans the EGE-1, EGE-2, and EGE-3 layers, reaching its maximum thickness at the contact with the EGE-4 layer. A portion of the petroleum products shows limited penetration into EGE-4, while the primary volume spreads laterally along the top of this layer in the direction of the general terrain slope.
3	3,6°	EGE-1, EGE-2, EGE-3, EGE-4	> 8 m	Similar to Section 1
4	1,2°	EGE-1, EGE-2, EGE-3, EGE-4	> 8 m	Similar to Section 2
5	4,0°	EGE-1, EGE-2, EGE-3, EGE-4	> 5 m	Similar to Section 1
6	4,3°	EGE-1, EGE-2, EGE-3, EGE-5, EGE-6	2-4 m	The predominant volume of petroleum products migrated via surface runoff, localized in plan along the fence line and building foundations. The portion of the contamination that infiltrated the soil filled the pore space laterally in the direction of the terrain slope, a process that prevailed over vertical infiltration. A zone of residual petroleum saturation has formed within the EGE-1 layer. The spatial distribution of the contaminant body significantly depends on the groundwater depth. In water samples from sources located uphill from Mohylivska Street (12 Kotelna St.; 49 Mohylivska St.; 43/1 Mohylivska St.), no exceedances of the maximum permissible concentrations (MPC) for petroleum products were recorded [12]. This indicates the absence of aquifer contamination in the middle and upper parts of the slope. Under high groundwater levels, the primary mobile phase body forms directly above the water table within the EGE-3 layer, where the capillary fringe restricts further vertical migration and facilitates lateral spreading. The thickness of the smear zone is determined by seasonal water table fluctuations and is approximately 0.3 m. In the case of deeper groundwater levels, gradual petroleum saturation of the EGE-3 thickness occurs, followed by potential local vertical breakthroughs through more permeable EGE-5 interlayers into the EGE-6 sands, leading to subsequent aquifer contamination. In both cases, lateral migration of the contamination occurs in the direction of the general terrain slope.

Sect.	Slope	Geo Log	GW	Contaminant body
7	0°	EGE-1, EGE-2, EGE-3, EGE-5, EGE-6	1,1-1,4	The formation of the contaminant body is determined by the shallow groundwater depth and the presence of a storm sewer collector, which acts as anthropogenic drainage. The contaminant body follows a "shark fin" model: the saturation peak is localized within the EGE-2 layer inside the capillary fringe, coinciding with or situated slightly above the water table, with decreasing saturation above and below this point. The thickness of the smear zone is determined by seasonal groundwater level fluctuations and is approximately 0.3 m. The combination of the petroleum spill with the onset of the flood temporarily restricted the spread of the contaminant body toward the floodplain. During the spring snowmelt, the infiltration flow from the slope created additional downward pressure, while the groundwater backwater from the floodplain acted from below. As a result, the contaminant body underwent primarily lateral expansion along Nemyshlianska Street. This hypothesis is corroborated by reports from residents at 258 Nemyshlianska St. regarding petroleum seepage through cracks in the sidewalk six months after the spill [12]. Following the recession of the water level, the established hydraulic gradient led to intensive contaminant migration toward the floodplain.

According to the engineering-geological survey materials [11], a clay layer acting as an aquiclude is observed in the valley, which may have a lenticular, non-homogeneous structure. Given the generalized nature of the geological and hydrogeological information, the proposed conceptual site model (CSM), which assumes an unconfined aquifer type, must be verified through the results of field investigations

Figure 16. Spatial distribution of the contaminant body in plan view along Urban Streets

6.3 The Nemyshlia River floodplain

The city storm sewer system discharges petroleum products into the Nemyshlia River floodplain at three locations:

- The Petenkivskyi Pond floodplain
- The Small Pond floodplain
- The Nemyshlia River channel downstream near the Traktorobudivnykiv Avenue bridge

Given that petroleum products have a lower density than water, they migrated primarily along the air–water interface until the interfacial tension forces at the front of the petroleum layer reached equilibrium. Considering the significant volume and location of the leakage, the contamination completely covered the floodplains of the Petrenkivskyi and Small Ponds and distributed deep into the floodplain in the area of the bridge over Traktorobudivnykiv Avenue.

The portion of petroleum products that entered directly into the river channel, which was not restricted by ice cover, was transported downstream by the current with subsequent spreading within the river system. The fact that petroleum concentrations in the river water at distances up to 27 km from the accident site exceeded MPC by 7–8 times [2] indicates that not only the dissolved phase but also significant volumes of free-phase petroleum products entered the river system.

Figure 17. Spatial distribution of the contaminant body in plan view within the Nemyshlia River floodplain

Another portion of the petroleum products that entered the floodplain as a floating layer was intercepted by a natural biogeochemical barrier. The restricted water exchange between the floodplain and the ponds, occurring only in localized areas, facilitated a reduction in water velocity, the accumulation of petroleum products in stagnant zones, and the coating of reed stems. As a result, the floodplain zone has formed a persistent secondary source of chronic contamination, which has led to the prolonged release of dissolved contaminant fractions into the river system.

According to the research results of reed bioplatoes in Oman [13], bottom sediments are capable of accumulating up to 45% of petroleum products by their own mass, and the aboveground reed biomass — up to 56%, whereas the soil matrix itself retains relatively low concentrations of around 15 mg/kg without significant further accumulation. Research results on the impact of heavily oil-contaminated soils on reed marshes at the Liaohe oil field [14] showed that after one growing season, heavy oil was predominantly concentrated in the reed root system. The contaminant body is localized within the near-surface organo-mineral layer of the bottom sediments and practically does not penetrate into the water-saturated soil matrix.

Accounting for the fire in the floodplain in the summer of 2024 and the two-year period of natural transformation, a secondary contaminant body has formed within the Nemyshlia River floodplain:

- In the bottom sediments, it is localized primarily within the rhizosphere of the reed root system and in the near-surface layer with a thickness of up to 0.6 m.
- During the spring flood, the rising water level enhances the infiltration of the dissolved phase into the soils of the Petrenkivskiy Pond coastal buffer zone, leading to the formation of secondary contamination in a state of residual saturation within the smear zone from the surface to a depth of approximately 1.2 m.

The results of the chemical composition analysis of aqueous extracts from bottom sediments in the Small Pond (5d) confirm the presence of petroleum products in quantities that exceed maximum permissible limits by up to 6.4 MPC [12].

6.4 Distribution of Contamination Volumes

It is impossible to determine the exact distribution of contamination volumes within the natural environment; however, according to preliminary estimates, the situation is as follows:

- Approximately 200 t (5%) was atomized, partially incinerated, and partially deposited on the surface as aerosol fallout over an area of about 400 ha during the initial hours of the accident
- Approximately 800 t (20%) infiltrated into the soil and filled the pore space of the soil matrix during surface migration over an area of about 2 ha
- Approximately 1,000 t (25%) spread across the surface waters of the Nemyshlia, Kharkiv, Lopan, and Udy rivers, covering an area of about 78 ha
- The bulk of the volume, up to 2,000 t (50%), accumulated in the bottom sediments of the Nemyshlia River floodplain over an area of about 10 ha

The estimate is based on a maximum-case petroleum leakage scenario, the exact volume of which has not been definitively established, and does not account for the reduction in contaminant mass resulting from natural attenuation processes: evaporation, dissolution, and biodegradation.

Figure 18. Spatial distribution of the contaminant body

7. Chemical Composition of the Contamination

Unacceptable risk to human health or the environment is determined by the concentrations of individual contaminant components rather than the total mass of petroleum products in the soil, the degree of saturation, or mobility indicators.

The contamination consists of a mixture of gasoline and diesel fuel—light petroleum products with distinct physicochemical characteristics.

Gasoline is a light petroleum fraction dominated by hydrocarbons in the C₄–C₁₂ range, characterized by high volatility, an increased proportion of low-molecular-weight aromatic and aliphatic compounds, relatively higher solubility of individual fractions in water, and the ability to rapidly form a vapor phase within the vadose zone.

Diesel fuel belongs to the middle distillate fractions dominated by C₁₀–C₂₂ hydrocarbons, characterized by lower volatility and lower water solubility, yet it possesses a higher affinity for sorption and adsorption onto organic matter and the soil mineral matrix.

Soil contamination assessment in cases of gasoline and diesel fuel spills is conducted based on the maximum permissible concentrations (MPC) of the following hazardous chemical substances, in accordance with the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine dated December 15, 2021, No. 1325 [15]:

Table 2

Substance Name	Maximum permissible concentration (MPC) standards, milligrams per kilogram of soil, accounting for background levels
Total Petroleum Hydrocarbons (TPH):	
For oil depot lands	1000
For other lands	500
Benzene	0,3
Toluene	0,3
Xylenes	0,3
Benzo(a)pyrene	0,02
Phenol (secondary product)	4
Styrene (secondary product)	0,1

Heavy metals may be detected in soils, groundwater, and bottom sediments; however, they are not diagnostic indicators of a gasoline or diesel fuel spill. Elevated metal concentrations within the contamination zone are most frequently associated with secondary processes—changes in redox conditions, environmental acidity, the development of anaerobic hydrocarbon degradation, and the mobilization of elements from the soil mineral matrix.

Maximum permissible concentrations (MPC) of pollutants in the ambient air of populated areas are summarized in the publication prepared by the Department of Atmospheric Air of Ukraine [18]

Table 3

Substance Name	Maximum permissible concentration (MPC) standards, milligrams per cubic meter of air, daily average
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Gasoline (petroleum, low-sulfur, calculated as carbon)	1,5
Benzene	0,1
Toluene	0,6
Ethylbenzene	0,02
Xylenes	0,2
Cumene	0,014

Given that the threats from the petroleum vapor phase are associated not only with public health impacts but also with explosion risks in cases of vapor accumulation within enclosed, small-volume basements of private houses, it is advisable to assess petroleum vapor concentrations in comparison with the lower and upper explosive limits (LEL/UEL).

Table 4

Substance Name	HKIIP (LEL, %)	BKIIP (UEL, %)	Flash point (°C)
Benzene	1,2-1,3	7,1-8,0	- 11
Toluene	1,1-1,2	7,1	+ 4
Ethylbenzene	0,8-1,2	6,7-7,8	+ 13
Xylenes	0,9-1,1	6,6-7,0	+ 27
Cumene	0,8-0,9	6,0-6,5	+ 31

According to Raoult's law, the equilibrium vapor concentration of an individual component above a petroleum product is determined by its mole fraction in the liquid hydrocarbon mixture and the saturated vapor pressure of the pure substance.

However, there is no universal concentration of petroleum hydrocarbons in either the dissolved or vapor phases that unequivocally indicates the presence of petroleum product contamination. This is due to the variability in the composition of petroleum products, the differing proportions of individual components in fuel mixtures, as well as the degree of physicochemical weathering, biodegradation, and mass transfer between phases. Consequently, the interpretation of monitoring results is based not on absolute threshold concentration values, but on their relationship to the theoretical effective solubility of components in the aqueous phase and on a lines-of-evidence approach characterizing the proximity of the hydrocarbon plume to the source zone.

According to the ITRC methodology [17], air concentrations exceeding 500 ppm for recent spills are considered a diagnostic indicator of a plume's potential location in close proximity to the source zone. Given that more than two years have passed since the petroleum spill, a more relevant criterion is the concentration of dissolved substances in groundwater at levels exceeding 1–5% of their calculated effective solubility, which also indicates the plume's proximity to the source.

Table 5

Substance Name	Mole fraction in the petroleum product	Molecular weight, g/mol	Saturated vapor pressure, Pa	Diagnostic indicator, mg/m ³
Benzene	0,03	78,11	10000	96-480
Toluene	0,15	92,14	2900	164-822
Ethylbenzene	0,05	106,17	930	20-100
Xylenes	0,15	106,16	900	59-294
Cumene	0,02	120,20	530	5-26

Assessment of groundwater and surface water contamination levels following a gasoline and diesel fuel spill is conducted in accordance with the hygiene standards for water quality in Category II water bodies, approved by the Order of the Ministry of Health of Ukraine dated May 2, 2022, No. 721 [16]:

Table 6

Substance Name	Maximum permissible concentration (MPC) standards, milligrams per cubic decimeter (mg/dm ³) of water
Total Petroleum Hydrocarbons (TPH):	
Sour crude	0,1
Heavy crude	0,3
Gasoline	0,1
Benzene	0,5
Toluene	0,5
Ethylbenzene	0,01
Xylenes	0,05
Naphthalene	0,01
Thiophene	2,0
Cumene	0,1
Phenol (secondary product)	0,001
Styrene (secondary product)	0,1

According to Raoult's law, the dissolved concentration of a petroleum product component in groundwater is the product of its concentration within the petroleum product itself and the solubility of the pure component in water—it does not depend on the petroleum product saturation of the soil matrix pore space.

To assess the theoretical effective solubility of components within the plume, a calculation of their maximum possible equilibrium concentrations in the aqueous phase was performed based on the mole fraction of individual components in the gasoline and diesel fuel mixture. According to the ITRC methodology [17], dissolved substance concentrations in groundwater exceeding 1–10% of their calculated effective solubility are considered a diagnostic indicator of the plume's potential location in close proximity to the source zone.

Table 7

Substance Name	Mole fraction in the petroleum product	Maximum solubility in water, mg/dm ³	Diagnostic indicator, mg/dm ³
TPH			> 30
BTEX			> 20
Benzene	0,03	1780	0,5-5,0
Toluene	0,15	530	1,0-8,0
Ethylbenzene	0,05	170	0,1-0,85
Xylenes	0,15	180	0,3-2,7
Naphthalene	0,08	31	0,02-0,25
Thiophene	0,03	400	0,15-1,2
Cumene	0,02	50	0,01-0,1

8. Spatial Distribution of Contaminant Plumes

Contamination threats can affect receptors through the adsorption of pollutants onto solid particles in the surface soil layer, as well as through the migration of contaminants in dissolved and vapor phases. Since the primary pathways of surface petroleum migration were partially obstructed by fences and building foundations, the contamination of surface humus layer areas used for agricultural production occurred predominantly through surface deposition of petroleum products during splashing at the moment of the explosion, as well as fallout from the aerosol cloud.

8.1 Dissolved phase contaminant plume in surface waters

The dissolved phase plume in the Nemyshlia River floodplain is forming as a multi-vector system. Dissolved pollutants saturate the surface water body within the confined volume of the floodplain and maintain elevated concentrations due to constant influx from the source zone localized in the bottom sediments.

Contaminated surface waters from the floodplain filter through a soil bund and enter the Petrenkivskyi Pond, where they accumulate. Simultaneously, a portion of the contaminated waters from the floodplain flows directly into the Small Pond. This causes an increase in petroleum product concentrations in the waters of the Small Pond, which is confirmed by chemical analysis results: on the eve of the flood, the petroleum product content reaches 1.5 MPC [12].

During snowmelt periods, the hydraulic connection with the channel intensifies, causing contaminated waters to be discharged into the Nemyshlia River. Dissolved hydrocarbons are entrained by the current, intensively mixed by turbulent flows, and form an elongated contaminant plume downstream, manifested by periodic increases in petroleum product concentrations at monitoring stations. This is confirmed by the pulsating nature of surface water contamination downstream near the bridge at 77 Krasnopilska St.: in late December and February, concentrations reach 6.1 MPC [12].

The ratio of recorded concentrations aligns with the hypothesis of preferential petroleum product accumulation within the Petrenkivskyi Pond floodplain, whereas the Small Pond shows relatively lower values, indicating its secondary nature of contamination.

8.2 Dissolved phase contaminant plume in groundwater

Taking into account the available information on the hydrogeological regime of the contaminated area, the formation of petroleum product plumes in groundwater is expected in the vicinity of Kotelna St. (section 6-7) and Zapovidna St. The presence of a plume is confirmed by the results of the chemical composition analysis of water from the wells at 256A Nemyshlianska St. (7k) and 9 1st Plidnyi Ln., where elevated petroleum product concentrations of 7.1 MPC and 16.8 MPC [12] respectively were recorded.

The dissolved phase plume is forming in the direction of natural groundwater flow — toward the discharge zone in the Petrenkivskyi Pond floodplain. Its presence is confirmed by the chemical analysis of water from the well at 256A Nemyshlianska St. (7k), where a petroleum product concentration of 7.1 MPC [12] was recorded.

During the spring flood period, the rising water levels in the wetlands cause groundwater mounding (backwater effect) and obstruct its natural discharge toward the floodplain. Under these conditions, a temporary shift in the hydraulic gradient occurs, causing the plume to realign along the valley — in the direction of Nemyshlianska St. The peak petroleum product concentrations of 16.8 MPC [12], recorded in late February in the well at 9 1st Plidnyi Ln., confirm this seasonal transformation of the plume configuration.

In the near-field zone of the plume, diesel components (naphthalene, thiophene) predominate, along with a portion of aromatic compounds with high initial concentrations (xylene, ethylbenzene, benzene). Conversely, the far-field zone is dominated by more soluble gasoline fraction components (benzene, toluene), as well as secondary transformation products (phenol, styrene).

Figure 19. Spatial distribution of the dissolved phase contaminant plume in surface and groundwater during a flood (petroleum product concentration in mg/dm^3 , standard limit — 0.1)

The dissolved phase plume is formed in the upper part of the aquifer, encompassing the entire interval of petroleum-saturated pores, including the smear zone. Its transverse dimensions are primarily determined by the lateral boundaries of the source zone and are expected to be slightly larger due to the transverse dispersion of groundwater. According to Darcy's law, the migration velocity of the contaminant plume with groundwater in the soil-vegetation layer is estimated at approximately 14 m/year under average annual conditions and can increase to about 46 m/year during the short period following the flood. Given the distance of approximately 130 m from the source zone to the floodplain, the dissolved phase plume has nearly reached the Petrenkivskyi Pond floodplain.

8.3 Dissolved phase contaminant plume in atmospheric precipitation infiltration waters

In the lowlands, groundwater exists permanently as a zone of accumulation and discharge, whereas on the slope, it is ephemeral in nature. Due to the high hydraulic gradient, water only flows transiently along the confining layer during precipitation events, failing to form a stable water table due to the lack of constant recharge (perched water). During this filtration through contaminated soils, individual petroleum components dissolve and transition into the aqueous phase, leading to the formation of dissolved hydrocarbon plumes in the direction of the topographic decline.

This accounts for the pulsating nature of contamination in wells and boreholes located in the middle part of the slope, specifically at 28 Plidna St. (up to 4.5 MPC), 9 1st Plidnyi Ln. (up to 16.8 MPC), and 16 1st Plidnyi Ln. (up to 3.0 MPC) [12], which is associated with the periodic influx of infiltration waters. In contrast, groundwater plumes typically exhibit a gradual decline in petroleum product concentrations as the soluble components within the source zone become depleted.

This regime indicates that the water intake structures are located outside the mobile saturation zone and are at a certain distance from the main contamination source, or that the petroleum products in the soil matrix are in a state of residual saturation following a surface spill.

If the wells directly intersected the mobile phase zone, dissolved petroleum product concentrations would remain consistently high without periods of complete natural attenuation. The lack of a direct correlation between precipitation and contamination levels is explained by the time lag in the infiltration plume migration, where the peak October rainfall of 122 mm [19] triggers the maximum concentration spike after a delay required to saturate the soil matrix and travel the distance from the source zone to the wells.

This aligns with the hypothesis that the surface contamination zone, formed by the splashing of petroleum products during the explosion, is localized within Plidna St. and 1st Plidnyi Ln.

The persistent nature of petroleum product contamination in the borehole at 129 Tankova St., ranging from 0.9 to 8.3 MPC [12], indicates its hydraulic proximity to the source zone.

Due to the fact that within the oil depot territory and along Yaseneva St. and Kotelna St. (section 1–5), the source zone is situated within the vadose zone and is confined by the EGE-4 layer—characterized by high density and low filtration capacity—the formation of a downward vertical dissolved phase plume under the influence of atmospheric precipitation infiltration is not expected.

8.4 Dissolved phase groundwater contaminant plume in the coastal zone during a flood

During the spring flood period, the sharp rise in water levels in the ponds triggers the infiltration of water enriched with the dissolved phase of petroleum products into the soils of the coastal buffer zone of the Petrenkivskiy and Small Pond floodplains. This leads to intensified vertical filtration and the secondary influx of dissolved petroleum products into the groundwater.

This mechanism likely explains the increase in dissolved petroleum product concentrations in the springs located at 54 Zapovidna St. (5k) and 66 Zapovidna St. (6k) to 4.3 MPC and 6.4 MPC [12], respectively. These increases occur synchronously with the rise of petroleum product content in the surface waters of the Small Pond to 1.5 MPC and the Nemyshlia River to 6.1 MPC [12] at the onset of the spring flood in February 2025.

8.5 Vapor phase contaminant plume

Vapor phase plumes form from volatile organic compounds (VOCs) above the source zone and the dissolved hydrocarbon plume due to their evaporation and diffusive transport within the pore air of the vadose zone. Through diffusion, volatile contaminant components migrate from areas of higher concentration to areas of lower concentration — from the subsurface zones of the source zone toward the ground surface and the atmosphere. This process becomes less significant as the contamination ages and the fraction of the most volatile components decreases.

9. Stability Assessment of the Contaminant Body and Plumes

After the active leak ceased, the hydraulic head of the petroleum products decreased rapidly, which ultimately limited the total volume of contamination available for lateral migration.

At high levels of pore space saturation, the mobility of petroleum products caused them to spread toward the periphery of the contaminant body. However, as saturation decreased, lateral migration gradually ceased. Stabilization of the contaminant body boundaries occurs when the petroleum entry capillary pressure into the soil matrix pores, combined with Natural Source Zone Depletion (NSZD) processes, compensates for the spreading gradient.

NSZD began immediately after the petroleum release through volatilization and dissolution, and over time, it has become most intense through biodegradation, continuing for more than two years.

Volatilization, dissolution, and biodegradation are components of natural attenuation, which encompasses the totality of physical and biogeochemical mechanisms for the redistribution and transformation of petroleum constituents into aqueous and gaseous phases, followed by their microbiological decomposition. Over time, these processes reduce the mass, saturation, and mobility of petroleum products.

The primary reduction in hydrocarbon mass occurs through biodegradation upon contact with microorganisms, as well as the degradation of dissolved components at the petroleum-water interface and volatile fractions after their transition into the gaseous phase. These processes are most pronounced in the unsaturated zone and the smear zone, where active mass transfer and oxygen access are ensured, whereas in the saturated zone, their progress is typically slowed due to differing geochemical conditions. As oxygen is depleted, microbes sequentially transition to using nitrates as electron acceptors, followed by manganese and iron oxides, and finally sulfates.

Biodegradation occurs throughout the smear zone through multiple mechanisms under both aerobic and anaerobic conditions. The gaseous byproducts of this reaction, carbon dioxide (CO₂) and methane (CH₄), are released directly into the vadose zone and do not enter the aqueous phase. As methane (CH₄) diffuses upward, it encounters oxygen (O₂) diffusing downward from the atmosphere, allowing indigenous methanotrophs and other microorganisms to consume the methane (CH₄), producing carbon dioxide (CO₂) and water vapor. Carbon dioxide (CO₂) efflux serves as evidence of the effectiveness of petroleum biodegradation processes.

The biodegradation effect of dissolved hydrocarbons can be observed in groundwater plumes by measuring changes in geochemical parameters: a decrease in dissolved oxygen (O₂), nitrates (NO₃-), and sulfates (SO₄²⁻), and an increase in dissolved ferrous iron (Fe²⁺), manganese (Mn²⁺), carbon dioxide (CO₂), and methane (CH₄).

According to the adopted Conceptual Site Model (CSM), petroleum products retain the potential for further migration only within the oil depot territory and in stagnant accumulation zones at section 2, 4, and 7. Within the floodplains, petroleum products have localized in the near-surface organo-mineral layer of the bottom sediments. In other areas along the main surface migration pathway, the spread of contamination is limited by the volume of soil infiltration.

Groundwater level monitoring results do not confirm the emergence of petroleum products in the investigated springs at new locations during the year of observation. Furthermore, chemical analysis

results for groundwater and surface water show no upward trend in dissolved petroleum component concentrations over time.

The absence of the mobile petroleum phase in the monitoring springs, the lack of an upward trend in groundwater concentrations, and the fact that two years have passed since the release, suggest a likely stabilization of the contaminant body boundaries and the formed dissolved phase plumes, with no signs of further expansion beyond the established contours.

Natural attenuation processes are expected to be most active in the surface contamination zone and within the soil matrix of residential and industrial areas. This is due to the contaminant body being primarily located in the vadose zone, as well as the intensive groundwater flow regime within the valley's discharge zone.

In the bottom sediments of the floodplain-pond zone, natural attenuation processes are extremely slow due to anaerobic conditions and sluggish water exchange. The high organic matter content in these sediments also radically slows the rate of natural depletion through hydrocarbon adsorption and sequestration. Organic matter firmly binds petroleum products within its matrix, drastically limiting their bioavailability to microorganisms.

Figure 20. Conceptual Site Model (CSM): Red – Contaminant Body, Blue – Dissolved Phase Plume, Green – Boundary of Local Surface Contamination Areas

Information regarding the quantitative assessment of the natural attenuation rate at the site is currently unavailable. At the same time, generalized data indicate that most measured values fall within a relatively narrow range. Specifically, an analysis of NSZD rates across 25 sites showed that in 50% of cases, the rates ranged from 6.5 to 26 t/ha/year [17].

The estimated timeframe for NSZD, at a rate of 16 t/ha/year in the residential and industrial zones and 8 t/ha/year in the floodplain-pond system, is approximately 23 years.

10. Identification of Contamination Concerns

Prioritizing remediation measures based on the developed initial Conceptual Site Model (CSM), the identification of potential contamination concerns has been conducted in the following areas:

- Human health and safety concerns: risks posed by the chemical composition of petroleum products, specifically the toxicity of aromatic hydrocarbons and the potential for explosive vapor concentrations to form in confined spaces
- Migration concerns: risks associated with a high degree of soil pore space saturation, which may lead to the migration of the free phase or the expansion of dissolved component plumes
- Regulatory compliance concerns: the necessity to adhere to legislative requirements regarding the maximum permissible concentrations (MPC) of petroleum products in ambient air, soils, bottom sediments, groundwater, and surface water.
- Physical, aesthetic, and social concerns: consideration of the requirements and expectations of stakeholders

According to the socio-economic assessment of the population in the Nemyshlianskyi district of Kharkiv, affected by the explosion and fire at the oil depot following Russian shelling, survey results indicate that 75% of the population is unemployed and facing severe financial hardship [8]. The survey revealed that residents detect petroleum volatilization, particularly during the warm season, and are forced to continue agricultural cultivation, which accounts for 30–70% of their household income.

Residents perceive health concerns arising from:

- Deterioration of ambient air quality in the surface layers during the summer period
- Deterioration of soil conditions used for agricultural cultivation
- Deterioration of water quality in the Nemyshlia River during the summer period
- Deterioration of drinking water quality

The primary expectations of stakeholders are:

- Obtaining objective information regarding the state of soil contamination on household plots and official conclusions on the feasibility of agricultural cultivation on these plots, as well as the quality of drinking water in wells and individual boreholes
- Remediation of soil cover from petroleum products to restore agricultural activities on household plots
- Remediation of the floodplain from petroleum products to ensure safe living conditions and health preservation

The level of priority and the urgency of response measures are determined by whether a completed exposure pathway to potential receptors has been established.

An exposure pathway is considered completed only when all necessary elements are present simultaneously. In such a case, a real risk of adverse impact is established, necessitating urgent restrictive and protective measures:

- Contaminant body or plume
- Migration pathway

- Presence of contaminant concentrations at the potential point of contact exceeding permissible standards
- Mechanism of intake into the organism or the structure of the receptor
- Receptor

In the absence of at least one of these elements, the exposure pathway is considered incomplete, allowing for a planned response without the immediate application of remediation measures.

The identified concerns have been verified based on the following indicators:

- Concentrations of petroleum products in soils, bottom sediments, surface water, and groundwater exceeding permissible levels, accounting for the pulse mode of contamination
- Location of receptors within a 6-meter zone along the surface migration pathway of petroleum products [17]
- Location of structures at a distance of less than 4.5 m above the contaminant body [17]
- Location of structures at a distance of less than 1.5 m above the contaminant plume [17]

Figure 21. Exposure concerns of the chronic phase of the petroleum product spill

Table 8

ID	Concerns	Nature of impact	Threshold indicators	Mechanism, scale, and receptor of impact	Location
1	Migration of the contaminant body	Continuous	Body stability	Potential health risk for residents of the Novi Domy residential area, associated with the contaminant body reaching the groundwater level on the slope	Oil depot and the adjacent territory located downslope
2	Migration of the contaminated surface water plume from the floodplain into the river system	Continuous	Plume stability	Health risk for approximately 43,900 residents of Kharkiv's coastal neighborhoods and 17 villages who use water for garden irrigation and meadow vegetation for livestock fodder Risk of degradation for 780,000 m ² of the ecosystem [5], encompassing aquatic and coastal flora and fauna	Coastal ecosystems of the Nemyshlia, Kharkiv, Lopan, and Udy rivers with a total length of 6.4 km
3	Migration of the contaminated surface water plume from the floodplain into recreational water bodies	Continuous	Plume stability	Health risk for Kharkiv residents who use 80,000 m ² of the recreational zone for leisure, swimming, and recreational fishing	Petrynkivskyi and Small Ponds
12	Migration of the contaminated groundwater plume from the valley into the floodplain	Continuous	Plume stability	Risk of secondary contamination of the floodplain	Floodplain of the Petrynkivskyi Pond
4	Soil matrix contamination	Continuous	500 mg/kg Less than 6 m from the primary surface migration pathway	Health risk for residents of 43 households who use the soil for agricultural production	Yaseneva St. 1, 42, Kotelna St., Tankova St. to the intersection with Mohylivskyi Ln., Mohylivska St. to the intersection with Kotelnyi Ln., Nemyshlianska St. 258, 256a, 256 and 254
5	Surface soil contamination	Continuous Discrete	0.1 mg/dm ³	Health risk for residents of 122 households who use the soil for agricultural production	Vysokohirna St., Plidna St. and 1st Plidnyi Ln. to the intersection with Velozavodska St.
6	Groundwater contamination	Continuous	0.1 mg/dm ³	Health risk for residents of 55 households who use water from wells, particularly for garden irrigation	Mohylivska St., Nemyshlianska St., Kotelnyi Ln., 1st Plidnyi Ln. to the intersection with Plidnyi Ln.

ID	Concerns	Nature of impact	Threshold indicators	Mechanism, scale, and receptor of impact	Location
7	Infiltration waters contamination	Intermittent	0.1 mg/dm ³	Health risk for residents of 122 households who use water from wells, particularly for garden irrigation	Vysokohirna St., Plidna St. and 1st Plidnyi Ln. to the intersection with Velozavodska St.
8	Groundwater contamination during flooding	Intermittent	0.1 mg/dm ³	Health risk for residents of 28 households who use water from wells, particularly for garden irrigation, and meadow vegetation for livestock feed	Zapovidna St.
9	Petroleum vapor intrusion into buildings located above the contaminant body	Continuous	soil thickness between the body and the building foundation is less than 4.5 m, distance from the surface migration pathway is less than 6 m	Health risk and safety for residents of 21 households due to the formation of explosive concentrations of petroleum product vapors in enclosed basement spaces	Mohylivska St. to the intersection with Kotelnyi Ln., Kotelna St. below Mohylivska St., Nemyshlianska St. 258, 256a, 256 and 254
10	Petroleum vapor intrusion into buildings located above the contaminant plume	Continuous	soil thickness between the plume and the building foundation is less than 1.5 m	Health risk and safety for residents of 23 households due to the formation of explosive concentrations of petroleum product vapors in enclosed basement spaces	Nemyshlianska St. 252, 250, 248, 246, 244, 242, 258a, 262, 262a, 264, 266, 268, 270, 1st Plidnyi Ln. 5, 7, 9, 11, 13, 15, Pidyomna St. 2, 3, 5, 7/3
11	Lack of objective and official information regarding the state of soil contamination on private plots	Continuous	official conclusions on the possibility of agricultural production on private plots and the quality of drinking water in wells and boreholes	Residents of the Nemyshlianskyi district	Households in the Nemyshlianskyi district affected by the petroleum spill

Given that soil sampling for total petroleum hydrocarbons (TPH) was conducted only in the surface layer to a depth of 1 m, monitoring wells for determining the mobile phase of petroleum products were not installed, and no analysis for the primary contaminants was performed, the identified threats are probable scenarios and require mandatory clarification based on the results of field investigations.

11. Remediation Strategy

The remediation strategy is formulated based on verified concerns identified within the developed conceptual site model (CSM), accounting for the degree and scale of their impact. The approach is oriented not toward the total removal of petroleum products, which is resource-intensive and not always technically feasible, but toward the elimination of specific risks associated with the presence of contamination.

Within the framework of the conducted assessment, concerns have been classified by the nature of their impact: risks to public health and safety, risks of further contaminant migration, the presence of the mobile phase of petroleum products, as well as aesthetic and social risks.

The presence of the mobile phase of petroleum products was highlighted as a distinct risk factor, as it is considered an active and long-term source of secondary contamination.

For each identified concern, a separate remediation goal has been defined. The remediation goal is formulated as achieving a target state of contamination where active management of the corresponding concern ceases, while the remediation objective defines the method for achieving that remediation goal.

Figure 22. Remediation strategy for the territory of the Nemyshlianskyi district of Kharkiv, which was affected by petroleum product contamination during the attack on the oil depot.

Table 9

ID	Concerns	Type of concern	Contamination indicators	Remediation goal	Remediation objective	Notes
1	Migration of the contaminant body	Migration risk	Saturation	Stop the migration of the contaminant body	Reduce the saturation of the soil matrix within the oil depot territory to residual (immobile) levels by removing the mass of the mobile petroleum phase to transmissivity indicators of 75 l/m/day [17] Monitored Natural Attenuation (MNA)	Given the site's location within an industrial zone with no sensitive receptors, once the contaminant body is localized, further measures may be limited to Monitored Natural Attenuation (MNA).
2	Migration of the contaminated surface water plume from the floodplain into the river system	Migration risk	Composition	Stop the migration of the dissolved petroleum constituent plume	Reduce plume migration using absorbent barriers and decrease petroleum product concentrations in the floodplain through enhanced anaerobic biodegradation a) in the dissolved phase: benzene – 0.5 mg/dm ³ , toluene – 0.5 mg/dm ³ , xylene – 0.05 mg/dm ³ , ethylbenzene – 0.01 mg/dm ³ , taking into account background levels b) in bottom sediments: benzene – 0.3 mg/kg, toluene – 0.3 mg/kg, xylene – 0.3 mg/kg, benzo[a]pyrene – 0.02 mg/kg, taking into account background levels	Excavation of bottom sediments will lead to large-scale secondary contamination of the river system and recreational water bodies. Establishing hydraulic barriers may lead to a rise in contaminated groundwater levels within the residential area and cause flooding of the coastal territory. The use of Total Petroleum Hydrocarbons (TPH) as an indicator of bottom sediment contamination is limited due to the significant presence of natural organic matter.
3	Migration of the contaminated surface water plume from the floodplain into recreational water bodies					
12	Migration of the contaminated groundwater plume from the valley into the floodplain	Migration risk	Composition	Stop the migration of the dissolved petroleum constituent plume	Reduce the concentration of petroleum products in groundwater by installing an electrokinetic barrier upstream of the floodplain: benzene – 0.5 mg/dm ³ , toluene – 0.5 mg/dm ³ , xylene – 0.05 mg/dm ³ , ethylbenzene – 0.01 mg/dm ³ , taking into account background levels	

ID	Concerns	Type of concern	Contamination indicators	Remediation goal	Remediation objective	Notes
4	Soil matrix contamination	Mobile contamination	Saturation	Removal of petroleum products to residual levels	Reduce petroleum saturation of the soil matrix along the primary surface migration pathway to residual levels, achieving transmissivity indicators of 75 l/m/day: a) Section 2-5: physical removal of the mobile petroleum phase mass AND b) Section 6-7: removal of the mobile petroleum phase along with groundwater pumping, OR c) Section 2-7: enhanced biodegradation	The selection of remediation methods is conducted taking into account the constraints imposed by dense residential development and limited access to private property. Extraction of petroleum products along with groundwater pumping will require the disposal of large volumes of waste.
5	Surface soil contamination	Health risk	Composition	Removal of the most toxic constituents	Reduce petroleum product concentrations in the humus layer of residential plot soils: benzene – 0.3 mg/kg, toluene – 0.3 mg/kg, xylene – 0.3 mg/kg, benzo[a]pyrene – 0.02 mg/kg, taking into account background levels: a) soil excavation, OR b) application of sorbents into the soil	Prior to remediation, a survey of residential plots must be conducted to identify potentially contaminated zones based on volatile organic compound (VOC) concentrations in soil vapor.
6	Groundwater contamination	Health risk	Composition	Reduction of petroleum product concentrations in the dissolved phase	Reduce petroleum product concentrations in the valley groundwater through enhanced biodegradation: benzene – 0.5 mg/dm ³ , toluene – 0.5 mg/dm ³ , xylene – 0.05 mg/dm ³ , ethylbenzene – 0.01 mg/dm ³ , taking into account background levels	The selection of remediation methods is conducted taking into account the constraints imposed by dense residential development and limited access to private property.
7	Infiltration waters contamination	Health risk	Composition	Removal of the most toxic constituents	Reduce petroleum product concentrations in the surface soil layer within the oil blast scatter zone: benzene – 0.3 mg/kg, toluene – 0.3 mg/kg, xylene – 0.3 mg/kg, benzo[a]pyrene – 0.02 mg/kg, taking into account background levels: a) soil excavation, OR b) application of sorbents into the soil	Prior to remediation, a survey of residential plots must be conducted to identify potentially contaminated zones based on volatile organic compound (VOC) concentrations in soil vapor.

ID	Concerns	Type of concern	Contamination indicators	Remediation goal	Remediation objective	Notes
8	Groundwater contamination during flooding	Health risk	Composition	Reduction of petroleum product concentrations in the dissolved phase	Reduce petroleum product concentrations in groundwater by establishing an electrokinetic barrier upstream of the floodplain: benzene – 0.5 mg/dm ³ , toluene – 0.5 mg/dm ³ , xylene – 0.05 mg/dm ³ , ethylbenzene – 0.01 mg/dm ³ , taking into account background levels	
9	Petroleum vapor intrusion into buildings located above the contaminant body	Health and safety risk	Composition	Reduction of volatile petroleum constituent concentrations in soil vapor	Reduce petroleum product concentrations in the soil matrix smear zone of the valley through enhanced biodegradation: benzene – 0.3 mg/kg, toluene – 0.3 mg/kg, xylene – 0.3 mg/kg, benzo[a]pyrene – 0.02 mg/kg, taking into account background levels	It is necessary to organize monitoring of explosive concentrations of petroleum vapors in the basements of residential buildings within the valley: benzene – 1.2%, toluene – 1.1%, xylene – 0.9%, ethylbenzene – 0.8%, cumene – 0.8%
10	Petroleum vapor intrusion into buildings located above the contaminant plume	Health and safety risk	Composition	Reduction of volatile petroleum constituent concentrations in soil vapor	Reduce petroleum product concentrations in the valley groundwater through enhanced biodegradation: benzene – 0.5 mg/dm ³ , toluene – 0.5 mg/dm ³ , xylene – 0.05 mg/dm ³ , ethylbenzene – 0.01 mg/dm ³ , taking into account background levels	
11	Lack of objective and official information regarding the state of soil contamination on private plots	Social risk		Ensuring residents' awareness regarding the actual state of contamination of residential plots	Conduct a survey of residential plots to identify contaminated zones based on volatile organic compound (VOC) concentrations in soil vapor	

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